

Public Perceptions of Police in Mizoram: A Study of Demographic and Contextual Variables

Lalthanmawia and Zonunsanga Colney

This paper is an attitudinal study that examines how demographic factors such as ethnicity, age, gender, education, occupation, and income and such contextual variables as police contact, corruption, fear of crime, police fairness, determine public perception of police in Mizoram that is one of the states of North East India. It is the first attempt of its kind that studies public attitude towards the police in Mizoram. The findings of this study show that the police are admired and revered by the people for their role in the state. The general public have positive attitude toward the police if their requests are met by the police. Those people who exhibit unequivocal appreciative view about the police are ready to help and cooperate with the police. This positive perception of the police has important implications for community policing in the state. Our research results concur with the findings of certain researchers that in small states of India like Manipur, Mizoram, Nagaland, Meghalaya, Sikkim and Tripura, people are generally happy with police performance. But police still need to adopt better and more people friendly approach so as to make the police-public relations more conducive to the successful implementation of community policing.

Keywords: Police, perception, demographic, contextual, community policing, Mizoram

Introduction

In the pre-independent India, a formal civil constabulary police system was established under the Police Act of 1861 or Act V of 1861 (Curry, 1932). But Indian police officers were perceived as unqualified or uneducated, underpaid, corrupted, extortionist, oppressive, inefficient, and disrespectful and they were unable to get the support and public partnership (Fraser et al., 1903; Scott et al, 2009). After independence, India inherited the existing police system that was based on military discipline, and highly authoritarian, serving the interest of the executive, and beyond the reach of the community (Joshi, 2013). Though literatures on Indian police are available yet there

Dr. Lalthanmawia and Zonunsanga Colney are Assistant Professors in the Department of Political Science and Department of Philosophy respectively at Lunglei Government College, Lunglei, Mizoram - 796701, India. [Email: lalthanmawiavt@gmail.com]

has been little research on citizens' perceptions of police in Mizoram. The present paper is an attempt to throw some light on the attitude of the people toward the police in Mizoram. It examines the influence of demographic factors such as ethnicity, age, gender, education, occupation and income and contextual variables like police contact, corruption, fear of crime, police fairness, on public perception of police in Mizoram.

Literature Review

Ever since the publication of 'Police Service Rating Scale' by Bellman (1935) police have always been subjected to critical analysis across the world. Though police perception research originated during 1930s yet it gained much popularity only in 1980s (Brown & Benedict, 2002) and it gained momentum with the adoption of community policing in some countries (Nalla & Madan, 2011). The success of community policing programs has been premised on the positive attitude of the citizens toward the police. (Greene & Decker, 1989. Brown and Benedict (2002) argued that negative attitude of the citizens toward the police must be addressed because it could have harmful impacts on the careers of police themselves, administrators and political leaders. In addition, it could lead to the outbreak of urban riots (Cox & Fitzgerald, 1996). Decker (1985) revealed that if the people were not happy with the police they were inconceivable to cooperate with them. Those citizens who have negative feeling about the police are less inclined to supply intelligence to the police; to help the investigating agency; to participate in the police initiated community policing programs; and to call for police help (Sampson et al., 1997; Tyler, 2004). But citizens' negative attitude can be improved with the help of community policing philosophy (Reisig & Giacomazzi, 1998). When the police and citizens hold mutual sympathetic attitude to each other they are expected to work together in crime prevention and reduction activities (Brooks et al., 1993). Following the research method designed by Decker (1981) criminology researchers of various countries measured public perceptions of the police with the help of individual and contextual variables (Greene & Decker, 1989). Individual level variables which determine citizen perceptions of the police include race, age, sex, education, and income (Greene & Decker 1989; Smith & Hawkins, 1973).

Recently, scholars took keen interest in studying the police performance in India. It was found that Indian police were uneducated, inefficient, underpaid, extortionist, oppressive, disrespectful and they did not receive public cooperation (Scott et al, 2009). While police perceptions research were frequently conducted by the western scholars, in India scientific research on this important subject seldom attracted the interest of scholars (Nalla & Madan, 2011). India took over the sub-standard police system which was corrupt and inefficient from the British (Joshi, 2013). In Mizoram though the Mizoram Police Act, 2011 authorises the State Security Commission to review and evaluate the performance of police forces yet the Commission has not conducted any meaningful study into the working of the police.

Demographic variables

Race

Among the individual level variables, race is always considered as one significant

predictor of perception of the police (Correia, Reisig, & Lovrich, 1996; Thomas & Hyman, 1977). A good number of criminal justice researches concluded that black viewed the police more negatively than white community (Hahn, 1969; Smith & Hawkins, 1973; Benson, 1981; Reisig & Park, 2006). But the influence of race is confounded by neighbourhood condition as there is variation in perception among the ethnic groups (MacDodald et al., 2007). For instance, black people in some neighbourhood tend to have more optimistic opinion of the police than white people (Jacob, 1971). In America, Hispanics viewed the police more positively than black citizens, nevertheless Spanish speaking Hispanics showed better willingness to help the police than their English-speaking counterparts (Cheurprakobkit, 2000). Moreover, minority community rated police performance very low relative to the majority section of the society due to fatalistic collision with the police (Walker, 1997).

Age

Age is another significant determinant of public perception of police across the world. There is a clear unanimity among the researchers that older citizens are inclined to perceive the police more positively than younger people (Cao, Frank & Cullen, 1996; Reisig & Giacomazzi, 1998; Chermak et al., 2001). On the other hand, younger generation view the police negatively (Hurst et al., 2000) because they are not happy with their contact with the police (Flexon et al., 2010); they could not tolerate curtailment of their freedom in any way and they often have painful encounters with the police (Gaines et al., 2015). Meanwhile there are a few scholars who asserted that age did not influence perception of the police (Parker et al., 1995)

Gender

There is no unanimity of findings among the researchers about the influence of gender upon citizen perception of police. Several scholars found that women always show favourable attitude to the police (Hadar & Snortum, 1975; Cao et al., 1996; Giacomazzi, 1998; Cheurprakobkit, 2000). On the contrary, men are said to be more sympathetic with the police than women (Brown & Coulter, 1983; Correia et al., 1996). In between these views, some researchers found that there is no differential perception of police between men and women (Reisig & Correia, 1997; Chermak et al., 2001; Benedict et al., 2000). As a result, it can be said that gender has little or a few predictive value for police perception (Gaines et al., 2015).

Education

Despite the findings of some researchers that downplayed the variable of education as a determinant of public evaluation of police, Correia et al., (1996) found that education and perception of police are closely related with each other. Their research showed that increase in the level of education improved public grading of police.

Socio-Economic Status

A good number of researchers found that people belonging to the lower socio-economic class are having more unfavourable opinion about the police than the well-to-do (Benson, 1981; Smith, 1981; Brown & Coulter, 1983; Cao et al., 1996; Sampson &

Bartusch, 1998). Conversely, it is also found that among the black community, the richer section was resentful of police (Boggs & Galliher, 1975). But in America both the blacks and the whites who belong to low income group, were pessimistic about the police, but while the whites' perception improved with their upward mobility in their status, the view of the black people remained negative irrespective of improvement in their economic position (Hagan & Albonetti, 1982). Thus the impact of socio-economic status on police perception is confounded by race (Brown and Benedict, 2002).

Contextual Variables

Contextual variables include victimization and fear, neighbourhood condition, and citizen-police contact (Web & Marshal, 1995).

Victimization and fear of crime

A large number of researchers found that crime victims often have a gloomy picture of police (Carter, 1985; Priest & Carter, 1999; Arthur, 1993). In addition, victims of violent crime are less happy with police response than victims of property theft (Cohen et al., n.d; Smith & Hawkins, 1973). As to the factor of fear of crime, several researchers pointed out that citizens who feel insecure in their community show negative attitude toward the police (Reisig & Giacomazzi, 1998). Further, fearful citizens are willing to give more and more power to the police (Mirandé, 1981). Paradoxically, there are some scholars who came up with the conclusion that fear of victimization does not have anything to do with police perception (Smith & Hawkins, 1973; Benson, 1981; Jackson et al., 2009).

Geographical location or Neighbourhood

Most researchers link public perception of police to neighbourhood variation (Jacob, 1971; Cao et al., 1996; Reisig & Giacomazzi, 1998; Reisig & Parks, 2000). People living in conflict-prone neighbourhood tend to develop anti-police mentalism (Macdonald et al., 2007; Weinrath et al, 2012). But Macdonald et al., (2007) reported that though different ethnic groups, for instance black and whites, live together in the same neighbourhood, they do not usually have same perceptions about police. Brown and Benedict, (2002) observed that variables such as education, race, income, employment status, and victimization confounded the relationship between police perception and neighbourhood effects.

Contact with the police

Citizen-police contact which also affects citizens' attitude toward the police, can be divided into two categories viz., voluntary (calling for police assistance, reporting crime, giving information to the police etc.) and non-voluntary which includes arrest, summon, fine etc. (Hinds, 2008). People show favourable attitude to the police as long as they have not come into contact with them. But when the number of citizen-police contact increases, citizens are usually unhappy with the police (Carter, 1985). Majority of research findings reported that positive contact with the police enhances public rating of police while negative one diminishes it (Worrall, 1999). Walker et al. (1972 and Chaurprakobkit (2000) observed that positive contact has stronger effects on public

evaluation of police but Jacob (1971) stated that negative contact is more powerful. Moreover, if the contact is initiated by the citizens (e.g. reporting crime or asking for assistance) they are likely to have favourable perception of police but citizens rate the police very low in case of police-initiated contact (arrest/fine) (Decker, 1981; Cheurprakobkit, 2000). Nevertheless, Rosenbaum et al., (2005) argued that dissatisfaction with police under citizen-initiated contact will have negative impact on police perception but it will have no impact under police-initiated contact. The people who witnessed police misconduct and excess, often have negative perception of police (Koenig, 1980; Cao & Hou, 2001).

However, the impact of citizen-police encounter on police perception is diluted by citizens' perception of the nature of police services. Several research findings show that crime victims rate the police high if they are satisfied with police actions and vice versa (Bordua & Tiftt, 1971; Smith, & Hawkins, 1973; Brandl & Horvath, 1991; Reisig, & Correia, 1997; Koster et al., 2015; Koster, 2016). Pate et al, (1976) reported that quick response to citizens call for police help results in positive perception of police. On the other hand, late and long response is associated with negative rating of police (Priest and Carter, 1999). But Brown & Coulter, (1983) stated that it is 'perception of response time', not 'actual response time' itself that determines public attitude toward the police. It is also important to remember that police-citizen contact is not a single determinant of police perception because people having negative or positive attitude toward the police, reported that they have never come into contact with police (Rosenbaum et al., 2005).

Present study: Context and Rationale

Mizoram, with a population of 1097,206 as per 2011 census is located in the North Eastern corner of India. (Statistical Handbook of Mizoram, 2020). When India achieved independence, the whole of Mizoram (Lushai Hills) formed one district of Assam having its own autonomous self-governing body in the form of District Council under VI Schedule to the constitution of India. From this time, it came under the control of Assam Police (Zothansanga, 2012). So long as it was within the administrative control of the state of Assam, the police forces were under the control of the Superintendent of Lushai Hills who had under him one Deputy Superintendent (Mizoram Police, n.d). Later, when Mizo District Council was given the status of Union Territory on 21st January, 1971 the present Mizoram Police was born with Mr. I.J. Verma, (IPS) as the first Inspector General (Dalidia, 2022).

Initially, police organization of Mizoram was based on the Police Act of 1861 (Act V of 1861) and the Criminal Procedure Code, 1973 (Act II of 1973). The Police Act, 1861 provided for the organisational structure and general duties of the police while the Criminal Procedure Code, 1973 dealt with the procedure and the manner in which the police would perform their functions like prevention of crime, arrest and investigation (Mizoram Police Manual, 2005). As per the directive of Section 2 of the Police Act of 1861, the whole territory of the state of Mizoram formed one police district and the power to determine the number of police force and the manner of recruitment was rested with the state government. (Police Act, 1861). After using Assam Police Manual for two decades, the Mizoram Police Manual was adopted in 2005 by the state

government. The organisational structure, powers and responsibilities, and operating procedure of the police are now determined by this manual. The new Police Manual of 2005 provides that the state police force shall be headed by the Director General of Police (DGP) but in due deference to Section 4 of the Police Act, 1861 which stated that the administration of state police should be vested in the hand of Inspector General of Police (IGP) and Deputy Inspectors General (IGsP), DGP is designated as the 'Director General of Police-cum-Inspector General of Police' (Mizoram Police Manual, 2005).

The state Legislative Assembly adopted the Mizoram Police Act in 2011. It is the first and the only Police Act that has been passed so far by Government of Mizoram. This Act provides for the present police organisational system and powers and functions of the Mizoram Police. Under the Act, the whole police force consists of unarmed and armed police forces. The main duty of civil constabulary police is to fight against crime while armed police forces help the civil police to deal with law and order problems, disasters and they are enjoined to perform any other functions as may be prescribed by the state government. They can be deployed by the DGP to deal with the problems of law and order anywhere.

The DGP who heads the Mizoram Police organization is appointed for a minimum period of two years by the state government from the among the three senior most police officers of the state (The Mizoram Police Act, 2011). He is assisted by Inspector Generals of Police. The entire territory of Mizoram is divided into 3 ranges viz., Northern, Southern and Eastern ranges. There are eleven police districts, 18 sub-divisions, 40 police stations, 3 Special Police Stations viz., Cyber Crime, Narcotic, and All Women. The Mizoram Armed police force consists of three Mizoram Armed Police battalions and five Indian Reserved Police battalions (Mizoram Police, 2020).

There is one police person for every 107.21 persons in Mizoram in 2021 which is better than national level, i.e., one police for every 515.59 persons. There are 1.87 police personnel for every square kilometre in the state (Bureau of Police Research and Development, 2021). As per the police record in 2020 there are 9006 police forces but the actual sanctioned post is 12,292.

The police receive support and confidence of the people in Mizoram. And the local civil society organisations like Young Mizo Association, Young Lai Association, Mara Thuytlia Py, Joint Action Committee of the villages etc., are often willing to help the police in dealing with crime and violence in the state (Goswami, 2009). The police are perceived positively in Mizoram (Paul et al., 2016). Despite the positive perception of the general public about the police, there have been many instances where the people are frequently at loggerhead with the citizens over the issues ranging from the desire of the youth section to snatch away the murderers or rapists from police custody to the question of protection of the interest of the Mizo community. Occasionally, students' protests against certain government policies always turned into violent clashes resulting in the killing of innocent citizens and public properties. Clashes between the local residents of Vairengte village and police over the decision of state government to divert the money sanctioned for the purpose of renovating Vairengte Police Station building in 2009, (Zozam Weekly, Sept, 28, 2009), and killing of one student in Chawngte in police firing in 2015 (Halliday, 2015) are recent examples.

Police are, sometimes, criticised for being the protector of the interest of government, not of the people. Allegations of police excess, violence, and corruption often appear in the media which are presumably going to downgrade the value of police in the state. Notwithstanding the occasional evaluation of police by media, there has been little or no systematic research that studies citizens' attitude toward the police in the state. No academic literature on the relationship between the police and the citizens has been published so far. Bearing this in mind, in this paper, we attempt to examine public perception of police. More precisely, this paper is an endeavour to examine the degree to which demographic and contextual factors predict the public perception of police in the state of Mizoram. This paper may contribute to the existing police research in India.

Materials and Methods

The present study is a descriptive and qualitative research. It relies on primary data and secondary sources. Univariate analysis and multivariate analysis methods were used in the present study.

Collection of Data and Sample: The primary data were collected during the months of May-July, 2022 from all eleven districts of the state of Mizoram. Questionnaires, written in both English and Mizo, were sent to the respondents who were selected using a combination of simple random, purposive as well as quota sampling method. The size of the sample was 242. Using purposive sampling, five major ethnic groups Mizo, Lai, Mara, Bru, and Chakma were selected as respondents. Mizos are chosen because majority of the population in Mizoram are Mizos. Lai, Mara and Chakmas were included in the sample because they are ethnic minorities having their own administrative bodies under the VI Schedule to the Constitution of India. Respondents were also selected from Bru community because they were one of the stake holders of police service in the state. These sampling groups may not be a true representative of the entire population in the strict sense of the term but the researchers believed that they may give a correct picture of public attitude toward the police in Mizoram. A sample was representative of different age groups, gender and socio-economic status of the total population.

Dependent Variable: In this study, the dependent variable i.e. public perception of police was measured with a single item: Do you think that the police are doing their job well?

Independent Variables: The present study employed two categories of independent variables which had been adopted by the previous researchers in police perception studies. The first category included individual characteristics such as age, ethnicity, gender, income, education, and occupation. Respondents were divided into four categories of age such as 1=below 18, 2=19-40, 3=41-60, 4=61 above. Ethnic community was categorized into five- 1=Mizo, 2=Lai, 3=Bru, 4=Chakma and 5=Maras. Gender was dichotomized into two- 1=Male and 2=Female. Individual monthly income was coded in four categories such as 1=Less than Rupees 30,000, 2=30,001-50,000, 3=50,001-

70,000, and 4=70,001 above. Education was given code number such as 1=below Class X, 2=Undergraduate, 3=Graduate, and 4=Post Graduate. Lastly, Occupation was categorized as 1= Government Employee, 2= Self Employed, 3= Student, and 4=Others. The first contextual variable employed in this study was police contact. The respondents were asked whether they have police contact, (0=No contact, and 1=Yes). They were also asked whether such contact was initiated by either police or citizens. The second contextual variable was police effectiveness against crime, drug or liquor control, and traffic management in the state. The respondents responded to the assertion that 'police are effectiveness' on a Likert Scale such as 1=Strongly Agree, 2= Agree, 3=Neutral, 4=Disagree, 5= Strongly Disagree. The next independent variable was the attitude of the police toward the rights of the people. They also responded to the statement that 'The police respect rights of the people'. Another contextual variable was police corruption which was measured with one item i.e. 'The police can be bribed' on a five point Likert Scale. The next neighbourhood variable, fear of crime was included to analyse personal and neighbourhood safety measured on a four-point scale such as 1=very safe, 2=reasonably safe, 3=somewhat unsafe, 4=very unsafe. The last independent variable was police fairness. The respondents were asked if the police were fair to everyone and ethnic minority, 0=No and 1=Yes. People's view about the police tendency to favour the rich and influential member of the society was assessed with the scale, i.e. 'The police show favour to the politicians, wealthy and influential members of the society' measured on a Likert Scale.

Drawbacks

Though this research study may offer a modest insight into the question of police image, it suffers from certain limitations. First, it ignores the factor of religion that is believed to have certain correlation with public view about police. Given the fact that majority of the state population are theocratic, future systematic researcher shall include this important independent predictor, i.e. religion.

Second, the present study suffers from methodological weaknesses. The readers are warned about our findings because sample are taken from educated citizens. Future studies of police shall also include the views of uneducated persons so as to produce more inclusive result.

Third, given the growing and pervasive influence of the media in shaping public opinion, no attitudinal or perception surveys can ignore the role of the media. Generally, citizens' opinion about the working of law enforcement agency is formed by their exposure to the media (Surette, 2010). Similarly, media shape public attitude toward the police. (Donovan & Klahm, 2015). Thus, it is clear that the present study has missed how media shape and nurture police image.

Fourth, another problem associated with this research is that people are seemingly reluctant to express their true opinion. While analysing data, some inconsistencies or lie are detected in their statements about the police. For instance, more than 71 percent of the total respondents found that the police are not fair and always discriminate against the poor while giving services to the people. Conversely, it is found that police have been fair to the ethnic minority communities of the state.

Analysis

Univariate Analysis

The characteristic features of the sample are given in Table 1. About 77.3 percent of the respondents identified themselves as Mizo, 7.9 percent were Lai, 2.1 percent Bru, 11.6 percent Chakma and 1.2 percent Mara. Nearly 6.6 percent of the sample were below 18 years of age, 55.8 percent fell into the age group of 19-40, 31.4 percent belonged to that of 41-60 and 6.2 percent were above 61. 66.5 percent of the sample were male while 33.5 percent were female. About 12.8 percent of the respondents were below class 10, 41.7 percent of them passed class X but were undergraduates, 25.2 percent were post-graduates. Nearly 22.7 percent were government employees, 20.7 percent were self-employed, and 40.1 percent were students. They were divided into four income groups. About 59.5 percent of the respondents reported that their family monthly income was less Rupees 30,000, 19 percent were in the income group of 30,001-50,000, 4.5 percent were in that of 50,001-70,000, and 12.6 percent earned more than 70,001.

Out of the total 242 respondents, 61.6 per cent held positive opinion and 37.2 percent showed negative attitude toward the police. As shown in Table 2, about 53 percent of citizens who initiated contact with the police revealed that they were happy with how the police respond to their request. On the contrary, 24 percent of them were not happy with police response. Police effectiveness against crime, and drug or liquor, as well as traffic management efficiency was measured on a Likert Scale. More than 50 percent of the respondents found that the police could deal effectively with crime. On the other hand, 10.8 percent reported that the police could not prevent crime while around 38 percent were neutral. About 32.2 percent of the respondents reported that the police could not deal effectively with the problems of drug and liquor in the state. Only 29.3 percent of them had faith in police ability to fight against drug and liquor while 38 percent preferred to be neutral. The police scored relatively high on the question of traffic control as 72.3 percent of respondents were pleased with how the police handled traffic problem. Police are universally subjected to criticism for violation of human rights in different countries of the world. Nevertheless, in Mizoram more than 53 percent of the respondents believed that police respected rights of the people whereas 10.8 percent viewed that human rights were often violated by the police.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics of Respondents (n=242)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coding</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Dependent Variable			
Attitude toward the Police	0=No (Negative)	90	37.2
	1=Yes (Positive)	149	61.6
Independent Variables			
Demographic Variables			
Ethnicity	1=Mizo	187	77.3
	2=Lai	19	7.9

	3=Bru	5	2.1	
	4=Chakma		28	11.6
	5=Mara		3	1.2
Gender	1=Male		161	66.5
	2=Female		81	33.5
Age	1=Below 18	16	6.6	
	2=19-40		135	55.8
	3=41-60		76	31.4
	4= 61 Above	15	6.2	
Education	1=Below class X		31	12.8
	2=Undergraduate		101	41.7
	3=Graduate	49	20.2	
	4=Post-Graduate		61	25.2
Occupation	1=Govt. Employee		55	22.7
	2= Self-Employed		50	20.7
	3= Student		97	40.1
	4=Others		40	16.5
Monthly Income	1=Less than 30,000		144	59.5
	2=30,001-50,000		46	19.0
	3=50,001-70,000		11	4.5
	4=70,001 Above		31	12.8
Contextual Variables				
Police Contact	0=No	190	78.5	
	1=Yes	51	21.1	
Effective Against Crime	1=Strongly Agree		23	9.5
	2=Agree		100	41.3
	3=Neutral		92	38.0
	4= Disagree	22	9.1	
	5=Strongly Disagree		4	1.7
Effective Against Drug/ Liquor	1=Strongly Agree		11	4.5
	2=Agree		60	24.8
	3=Neutral		92	38.0
	4= Disagree	62	25.6	
	5=Strongly Disagree		16	6.6
Effective in Traffic management	1= Strongly Agree		39	16.1
	2=Agree		136	56.2
	3=Neutral		51	21.1
	4=Disagree	11	4.5	
	5=Strongly Disagree		4	1.7
Respect rights	1=Strongly Agree		13	5.4
	2=Agree		117	48.3
	3=Neutral		84	34.7
	4=Disagree	22	9.1	
	5=Strongly Disagree		4	1.7

Police are Corrupted	1=Strongly Agree	20	8.3
	2=Agree	69	28.5
	3=Neutral	117	48.3
	4=Disagree	24	9.9
	5=Strongly Disagree	7	2.9
Fear of Crime (Citizens are safe)	1=Very Safe	51	21.1
	2=Reasonably Safe	108	44.6
	3=Somewhat Unsafe	65	26.9
	4=Very Unsafe	16	6.6
Police Fairness	0=No	189	78.1
	1=Yes	47	19.

Source: Primary Data

Even though Verma (1999) reported that corruption had been prevalent in all police departments throughout India and it permeated every level of police organization from constable to the top officers. But only about 36 percent of the respondents reported that police involved in corruption and illegal activities in the state of Mizoram while 48.3 percent of them refused to disclose their opinion on the issue of corruption.

Meanwhile public perception of police with respect to fear of crime was positive as 65.7 percent of the respondents felt safe and secure while going out on the street at night. On the question of fairness, 72.8 percent of the respondents found the police unfair to the people. Majority of the respondent found that police were fair to the minority. About 66 percent of them replied that the police were partial in favour of the rich and wealthy, and influential politicians of the state.

Multivariate Analysis

After univariate analysis of the data, Binary Logistic Regression Analysis was carried out to examine how demographic and contextual variables predict citizens' perception of police in the state of Mizoram. Demographic variables include ethnicity, gender, age, education, occupation, and monthly income. The contextual predictors like police contact, ability or effectiveness of police to fight crime, drug or liquor, and traffic management, corruption, fear of crime, police presence on the street, fairness and partiality were also included. Data were analysed using statistical software called IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0. Binary Logistic Regression Analysis model was preferred due to the dichotomous nature of the dependent variable, i.e. public of perception of police which could be either positive or negative. All responses were condensed into two response categories. Strongly Agree and Agree were combined into 'Yes' category and Strongly Disagree and Disagree into 'No' category. Neutral response was included in the latter category due to the fact that if respondents were not willing to express opinion, their neutral response was taken to mean negative.

Table 3 showed that ethnicity was not a significant determining factor of citizens' attitude toward the police ($t = .986$ or $p > 2.132$). One ethnic minority, Lai held a gloomier perception of police than majority Mizo which was a reference category (standardized regression coefficient or $EXP(b) = .911$). Bru held a positive notion while Chakma and

Table 2
Public Perception of Police in Mizoram

<i>Variable</i>	<i>SA+A/n %</i>	<i>Neutral/n %</i>	<i>D+SD/n %</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>
Independent Variables					
Police Contact					
I am happy with police response to my request	129/53.3	0/0	58/24	.69	.464
Police Effectiveness					
The police are effective against crime	123/50.8	92/38	26/10.8	2.52	.852
The police are effective against drug/liquor	71/29.3	92/38	78/32.2	3.05	.978
The Police manage traffic efficiently	175/72.3	51/21.1	15/6.2	2.19	.820
Police Attitude toward Right					
The police respect rights of the people	130/53.7	84/34.7	26/10.8	2.53	.802
Corruption					
The police can be bribed	89/36.8	117/48.3	31/12.8	2.70	.873
Fear of Crime/Safety					
I feel safe when I go out alone at night	159/65.7	0/0	81/33.5	2.19	.846
Police Fairness					
The police are fair	47/19.4	0/0	189/78.1	.20	.400
Police are fair to minority	130/53.7	0/0	99/40.9	.20	.400
Police favour politicians and wealthy persons	160/66.1	66/27.3	15/6.2	2.11	.951

Source: Primary Data
(SA+A= Strongly Agree + Agree, D+SD Disagree + Strongly Disagree)

Mara were dissatisfied with the police. In this study it is found that female respondents had more positive attitude toward the police than their male counter parts (reference category). With an increase in age ($b=.508$), respondents had the likelihood of having more positive perception of police. Another predictor, education with $.244$ coefficient showed that with an increase in the educational level, police perception was becoming more positive. On the scale of employment status, students were more dissatisfied with the police than employed persons (reference category). Self-employed persons and others occupational groups like driver or daily labourers had more positive opinion about police than government employees. Respondents who were in the higher income brackets showed more appreciative view about the police than those belonging to lower income groups.

With respect to contextual predictors Table 3 showed that an increase in the number of police contact resulted in lower rating of the police in the state ($b= -.257$). Those respondents who initiated contacts (voluntary contact) with the police like calling for police assistance or filing FIRs in the Police Stations, were not happy with the police ($b=-.832$). However, among the respondents who received prompt and timely response from the police had a high positive feeling about the police, ($b= 1.381$). And those respondents who came into non-voluntary contact with police such as arrest had negative police image ($b= -.257$). Moreover, when the number of contact with police increased, there was possibility of having ill feeling about the police ($b= -.027$).

Those respondents who found that the police were able to control crime, drug, liquor, and traffic problems had optimistic police image. It is also found that if the police were respectful toward rights, people would have higher satisfaction ($b=.191$). Meanwhile, corruption could tarnish police image to a great extent. The analysis of data also showed that people who found that police were corrupted exhibited pessimistic perspective of police ($b= -.581$). And people who were fearful and felt insecure in their locality or neighbourhood had an unfavourable disposition toward the police ($b=-.209$). The presence of police on the street improves public perception of the police $b= .90$. Moreover, respondents who believed that police were fair, held a favourable perception of police ($b=1.927$). This study also revealed that if the police were partial in favour of the rich, politicians, and the influential members of the community, people would hold negative opinion about the police.

Table 3 Binary Logistic Regression: Public Perception of Police

Variables	b	S.E	Wald	df	Sig.	EXP(b)	95% C.I	
							Lower	Upper
Ethnicity			.358	4	.986			
<i>Lai</i>	-.093	1.139	.007	1	.935	.911	.098	8.488
<i>Bru</i>	.646	1.336	.233	1	.629	1.907	.139	26.181
<i>Chakma</i>	-.199	.691	.083	1	.774	.820	.212	3.175
<i>Maras</i>	-22.397	40192.97	.000	1	1.00	.000	.000	.

Gender (Female)	.412	.538	.586	1	.444	1.509	.526	4.330
Age	.508	.419	1.472	1	.225	1.662	.731	3.779
Education	.244	.242	1.022	1	.312	1.277	.795	2.051
Occupation			1.463	3	.691			
<i>Self-Employed</i>	.338	.731	.214	1	.643	1.403	.335	5.874
<i>Student</i>	-.437	.768	.323	1	.570	.646	.143	2.911
<i>Others</i>	.285	.702	.164	1	.685	1.330	.336	5.267
Monthly Income	.032	.243	.018	1	.894	1.033	.642	1.662
Police Contact	-.257	.578	.197	1	.657	.774	.249	2.403
<i>Voluntary Contact</i>	-.832	.587	2.011	1	.156	.435	.138	1.374
<i>Police Response</i>	1.381	.493	7.841	1	.005	3.978	1.513	10.455
<i>Non-Voluntary Contact</i>	-.543	.536	1.023	1	.312	.581	.203	1.663
<i>Contact Frequency</i>	-.027	.246	.012	1	.913	.973	.601	1.576
Crime Fighting	.576	.390	2.183	1	.140	1.779	.828	3.821
<i>Drug / Liquor Fighting</i>	.364	.542	.452	1	.501	1.439	.498	4.161
<i>Traffic Management</i>	.229	.466	.241	1	.624	1.257	.504	3.134
Police Attitude toward Rights	.191	.478	.160	1	.689	1.211	.475	3.088
Corruption	-.581	.462	1.580	1	.209	.559	.226	1.384
Fear of Crime	-.209	.514	.166	1	.684	.811	.296	2.220
Police Presence	.290	.446	.423	1	.515	1.336	.558	3.200
Fairness of Police	1.927	.883	4.765	1	.029	6.867	1.217	38.731
Police Partiality	-.432	.638	.458	1	.499	.649	.186	2.267
Constant	-1.666	1.852	.809	1	.368	.189		

Source: Primary Data

Note: b=regression coefficient; S.E.= Standard error; df=Degree of freedom; sig.=Significance; EXP(b)= Standardized regression coefficient.

The model summary shows that 44 percent of change in dependent variable is determined by independent variables. However, among all demographic and contextual variables in the model, only one i.e. police response ($t = .005$) is statistically a significant predictor of police perception. All predictor variables were not statistically significant determinants of police perception because their significance is more than .005.

Discussion

This is one of the first police perception study in Mizoram that explores how the police

are perceived by the people in this tiny state of India. The findings of this paper are significant in as much as it takes into account well-proven determinants of public perception of police which have been tested by researchers across the world. The same variables are replicated here. The people are always ready to join hands with the police if the police are trustworthy. The individual and contextual variables employed in this study are not only statistically significant factors of citizens' perception of the police but also determinants of public willingness to help the police (Nalla & Madan, 2011). But they are not having statistical significance in the context of Mizoram.

The bivariate analysis of data shows that despite the occasional confrontations with the citizens and custodial violence, about 61 percent of the respondents hold positive attitude toward the police. Our research results concur with the findings of certain researchers that in small states of India like Manipur, Mizoram, Nagaland, Meghalaya, Sikkim and Tripura (Paul et al. 2016) people are generally happy with police performance. The Mizoram Police forces are able to prevent and control crime effectively. Human rights violation or abuse of authority at the hands of police is a rare incident. The traffic police are polite and efficient. They ensure the smooth flow of vehicles along the narrow and congested road. And Mizoram is a safe place because people are not afraid of using the street at night. The study also reveals that people feel safe and secure when they see the police on the street patrolling their neighbourhoods.

Though majority of the respondents were silent on the question of police corruption, analysis of data shows that police are not free from corruption. They are not an impartial law enforcement agency. They tend to favour influential politicians and richer sections of the society.

In some western countries like USA it was found that women had negative perception of police (Correa et al, 1996), but in Mizoram it is found that women are predicted to have more satisfaction with the police. Similarly, age, education and income improve public perception of the police.

Among the contextual variables, there are a few factors which have negative impact. They are contact with police, police corruption, fear of crime and police partiality. But if the police are able to fight crime and if they are free from corruption, people are likely to be happy with them. Besides, increasing police presence on the street and fairness of the police are found to increase public happiness with the police. As Brown and Benedict (2002) pointed out it is imperative for the different stakeholders to address the above negative forces. If these impeding factors are ignored by the concerned authorities, police-community relations may suffer.

However, more than 95 percent of the respondents show that they are disposed to coalesce with the police against crime. This positive perception of the police is highly conducive to the successful working of community policing institution, i.e. the Village Defence Party. In Mizoram people are generally interested in the enforcement of law and order in their communities. They have been ready to help law enforcement agency. This may be ascribed to the positive relations between them and police.

However, as Reddy & Reddy (2007) said, Mizoram police are not perfect and they should try to adopt better and more people friendly approach so as to make the police-public relations more conducive to the success of community policing in the state.

While analysing perception of police we should remember that public faith in the police is gambled on their confidence in the government (Stack & Cao, 1998). As and when the local citizens lost their confidence in the ability of government law enforcement agency they tend to resort to community self-policing and self-protective mechanism. As stated by Baker (2010), local residents are compelled to make additional endeavours to protect themselves from criminals when protective services provided by the police are insufficient.

Conclusion

The present study analyses the impact of different determinants of citizens' perception of police such as demographic characteristics of the individuals and contextual variables. It analyses how the police are rated by the large stakeholders of criminal justice system, the community. Findings show that police are held in high esteem by the people and people trust the ability and efficiency of the police to fight against crime, fear of crime, drug menace and problem of liquor. Mizoram police are one of the best in India. People are happy with the overall performance of the police. Their performance in traffic control and management earns them nationwide laurels. But they are not spotless government security agency. A few respondents of the research found that they were corrupted and easily enticed by wealthier sections of the community with the decoy of some pecuniary benefits.

References

- Arthur, J. A. (1993). Interpersonal violence, criminal victimization and attitudes toward police use of force. *International Review of Modern Sociology*, 23(1), 91-106 <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41421597>
- Baker, B. (2010). Nonstate Policing: Expanding the scope for tackling Africa's urban violence. *Africa Center for Strategic Studies*, No. 7, September, 1-8 <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep19075>
- Bellman, A (1935). Police service rating scale. *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology* 26(1), i-viii. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1135366>.
- Benedict, E.R, Brown, B., & Bower, D.J. (2000). Perceptions of the police and fear of crime in a rural setting: Utility of a geographically focused survey for police services, planning and assessment. *Criminal Justice Policy Review*, 11(4), 275-298. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0887403400011004001>
- Benson, P.R. (1981). Political alienation and public satisfaction with police services. *The Pacific Sociological Review*, 24(1), 45-64. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1388792>
- Boggs, S. L., & Galliher, J. F. (1975). Evaluating the police: A comparison of black street and household respondents. *Social Problems*, 22(3), 393-406. <https://doi.org/10.2307/799819>
- Bordua, D. J., & Tiffit, L. L. (1971). Citizen interviews, organisational feedback, and police-community relations decisions. *Law & Society Review*, 6(2), 155-182. [<https://doi.org/10.2307/3052850>]
- Brandl, S.G., & Horvath, F. (1991). Crime-victim evaluation of police investigating performance. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 19(2), 293-305.

- Brooks, L., Piquero, A., & Cronin, J. (1993). Police officer attitudes concerning their communities and their roles: A comparison of the two suburban police departments. *American Journal of Police*, 12(3), 115-139.
- Brown, K., & Coulter, P. B. (1983). Subjective and objective measures of police service delivery. *Public Administration Review*, 43(1), 50-58. <https://doi.org/10.2307/975299>
- Brown, B & Benedict, W.R. (2002). Perceptions of the police: Past findings, methodological issues, conceptual issues and policy implications. *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*, 25(3), 543-580. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13639510210437032>
- Bureau of Police Research and Development (2021). *Data on police organization, 2021*. <https://bprd.nic.in>. (Accessed: 21 June 2022)
- Cao, L., Frank, J., & Cullen, F.T. (1996). Race, community context and confidence in the police. *American Journal of Police*, 15(1), 3-22. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07358549610116536>
- Cao, L., & Hou, C. (2001). A comparison of confidence in the police in China and in the United States. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 29(2), 87-99. [https://doi:10.1016/S0047-2352\(00\)00084](https://doi:10.1016/S0047-2352(00)00084)
- Carter, D. L. (1985). Hispanic perception of police performance: An empirical assessment. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 13(6), 487-500. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2352\(85\)90078-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2352(85)90078-9)
- Chermak, S., McGarrell, E.F., & Weiss, A. (2001). Citizens' perceptions of aggressive traffic enforcement strategies. *Justice Quarterly*, 18(2), 365-391.
- Cheurprakobkit, S. (2000). Police citizen contact and police performance: Attitudinal differences between Hispanics and Non-Hispanics. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 28(4), 325-336. [https://doi:10.1016/S0047-2352\(00\)00042-8](https://doi:10.1016/S0047-2352(00)00042-8)
- Cohen, I.M., Plecas, D. & McCormick, A. (n.d). Public safety, victimization, and perceptions of the police in 8 RCMP jurisdictions in British Columbia. *School of Criminology and Criminal Justice, University-College of the Fraser Valley*. <https://www.ufv.ca/media/assets/ccjr/reports>
- Correia, M.E., Reisig, M.D., & Lovrich, N.P. (1996). Public perceptions of state police: An analysis of individual-level and contextual variables. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 24(1), 17-28.
- Cox, S.M. & Fitzgerald, J.D. (1996). *Police in community relations: Critical issues* (3rd ed.). The McGraw-Hills Companies Inc.
- Curry, J.C. (1932). *Indian Police*. Faber and Faber Limited.
- Dalidia, E. (2022, January). 50 Mizoram police raising day: All you need to know about its history & achievements. *North East Today*. <https://www.northeasttoday.in/2022/01/21/50-mizoram-police-raising-day-all-you-need-to-know-about-its-history-achievements/>
- Decker, S.H. (1981). Citizen attitudes toward the police: A review of past findings and suggestions for future policy. *Journal of Police Science and Administration*, 9(), 80-87.

- Decker, S.H. (1985). The Police and the public: Perceptions and policy recommendations. In Homant, J.R. & Kennedy, D.B. (Eds.), *Police and law enforcement, 1975-1981*, Vol 3. (pp. 89-105). AMS Press.
- Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Mizoram. *Statistical Handbook of Mizoram, 2020*. <https://des.mizoram.gov.in>
- Donovan, K.M & Klahm, C.F. (2015). The role of entertainment media in perceptions of police use of force. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 42(12), 1261-1281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093854815604180>
- Dunham, R.G., & Alpert, G.P. (1988). Neighbourhood differences in attitudes toward policing: Evidence for a mixed-strategy model of policing in a multi-ethnic setting. *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 79(2), 504-523. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1143473>
- Flexon, J.L., Lurigio, A.J., & Greenleaf, R.G. (2010). Exploring the dimension of trust in the police among the Chicago juveniles. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 37(2), 180-189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2009.02.006>
- Fraser, A.H.L., Candy, J., Singh, R., Raghavaiyengar, B.S.S., Montgomery, J.A.L., Colvin, W.M., Kin, A.C.H., & Stuart, H.A., (1903). *Report of the Indian Police Commission, 1902-03*. Government Central Printing Office.
- Gaines, L., Kappeler, V., & Vaughn, J. (2015). *Policing in America*. Routledge.
- Goswami, N. (2009). India's counter insurgency experience: The 'trust and nurture' strategy. *Small Wars & Insurgencies*, 20(1), 66-86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09592310802573475>
- Greene, J.R. & Decker, S.H. (1989). Police and community perceptions of the community role in policing: The Philadelphia experiment. *The Howard Journal*, 28(2), 105-123.
- Hadar, I. & Snortum, J. (1975). The eye of the beholder: Differential perceptions of police by the police and the public. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 2(1), 37-54. <https://doi.org/10.1177/009385487500200103>
- Hagan, J., & Albonetti, C. (1982). Race, class, and the perception of criminal injustice in America. *American Journal of Sociology*, 88(2), 329-355. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2779552>
- Hahn, H. (1969). Ghetto sentiments on violence. *Science & Society*, 33(2), 197-208. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40401413>
- Halliday, A. (2015, August 4). Student killed in police firing in Mizoram's Chakma region headquarters. *The Indian Express*. <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/india-others/student-killed-in-police-firing-in-mizorams-chakma-region-headquarters/>
- Hinds, L. (2008). Public satisfaction with police: The influence of general attitudes and police-citizen encounters. *International Journal of Police Science & Management*, 11(1), 54-66. <http://doi.org/10.1350/ijps.2009.11.1.109>
- Hurst, Y.G, Frank, J., & Browning, S.L. (2000). The attitude of juveniles toward the police: A comparison of black and white youth. *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*, 23(1), 37-53.

- Jacob, H. (1971). Black and white perceptions of justice in the city. *Law and Society Review*, 6(1), 66-90. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3052913>
- Jackson, J., Bradford, B., & Hohl, K. (2009). Does the fear of crime erode public confidence in policing? *Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice* 3(10), 100-111. <https://doi.org/10.1093/police/pan079>
- Joshi, G.P. (2013). *Policing in India*. Atlantic Publishers & Distributions (P) LTD.
- Koenig, D.J. (1980). The effects of criminal victimization and judicial or police contacts on public attitudes toward local police. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 8(4), 24-249. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2352\(80\)90004-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2352(80)90004-5)
- Koster, N. (2017). Victims' perceptions of the police response as a predictor of victim cooperation in the Netherlands: A prospective analysis. *Psychology, Crime & Law*, 23(3), 201-220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1068316X.2016.1239098>
- Koster, N., Kuijpers, K.F., Kunst, J.J.M., & Van deur Leun, J.P. (2015). Crime victims' perception of police behaviour, legitimacy and cooperation: A review of the literature. *An International Journal of Evidence-based Research, Policy, and Practice*, 11(3), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15564886.2015.1065532>
- MacDonald, J., Stokes, R. J., Ridgeway, G., & Riley, K. J. (2007). Race, neighbourhood context and perceptions of injustice by the police in Cincinnati. *Urban Studies*, 44(13), 2567-2585. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43197602>
- Mizoram Police, (2020). *E-Book, 2019-2020*. <https://police.mizoram.gov.in>.
- Mizoram Police (n.d). *Police Headquarters: Brief history*. <https://police.mizoram.gov.in/police-headquarters-phq>
- Mirandé, A. (1981). The Chicano and the law: An analysis of community-police conflict in an urban Barrio. *The Pacific Sociological Review*, 24(1), 65-86. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1388793>.
- Nalla, K.N & Madan, M (2012). Determinants of citizens' perceptions of police-community cooperation in India: Implications for community policing. *Asian Journal of Criminology*, 7(4), 277-294.
- Parker, K. D., Onyekwuluje, A. B., & Murty, K. S. (1995). African Americans' attitudes toward the local police: A multivariate analysis. *Journal of Black Studies*, 25(3), 396-409. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2784645>
- Pate, T., Ferrara, A., Bowers, R.A., & Lorence, J. (1976). *Police response time: Its determinants and effects*. Police Foundation.
- Paul, D., Agarwal, P.A., & Chakraborty, S. (2016). Performance appraisal of Indian state police forces using ARAS method. *Management Science Letters*, 6(5), 361-372 <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2016.3.001>.
- Priest, T.B., & Carter, D.B. (1999). Evaluations of police performance in an African American sample. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 27(5), 457-465. [http://doi.org/10.1016/s0047-2352\(99\)00016-1](http://doi.org/10.1016/s0047-2352(99)00016-1)
- Reddy, P.L. S & Reddy, P.C. S. (2007). *Peace and development in North East India: A virtuous spiral*. Mittal Publications.

- Reisig, M.D. & Correia, M.E. (1997). Public evaluations of police performance: An analysis across three levels of policing. *Policing: An International Journal*, 20(2), 311-325. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13639519710169153>
- Reisig, M.D. & Giacomazzi, A.L. (1998). Citizen perceptions of community policing: Are attitudes toward police important? *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*, 21(3), 547-561. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13639519810228822>
- Reisig, M.D. & Parks, R.B. (2000). Experience, quality of life, and neighbourhood context: A hierarchical analysis of satisfaction with the police. *Justice Quarterly*, 17(3), 607-630. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07418820000094681>
- Reisig, M.D. & Chandek, S. M. (2001). The effects of expectancy disconfirmation on outcome satisfaction in police citizen encounters. *Policing: An International Journal*, 24(1), 88-99. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13639510110382278>
- Rosenbaum, D. P., Schuck, A. M., Costello, S. K., Hawkins, D. F., & Ring, M. K. (2005). Attitudes toward the police: The effects of direct and vicarious experience. *Police Quarterly*, 8(3), 343-365. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098611104271085>
- Sampson, R.J., Raudenbush, S.W., & Earls, F. (1997). Neighbourhoods and violent crime: A multi-level study of collective efficacy. *Science*, 277(5328), 918-924. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.277.5328.918>
- Sampson, R. J., & Bartusch, D. J. (1998). Legal cynicism and (subcultural?) tolerance of deviance: The neighbourhood context of racial differences. *Law & Society Review*, 32(4), 777-804. <https://doi.org/10.2307/827739>
- Scott, J., Evans, D. & Verma, A. (2009). Does higher education affect perceptions among police personnel? A response from India. *Journal of Contemporary Criminal Justice*, 25(2), 214-236. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043986209333592>
- Smith, P. E., & Hawkins, R. O. (1973). Victimization, types of citizen-police contacts, and attitudes toward the police. *Law & Society Review*, 8(1), 135-152. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3052811>
- Smith, J.M. (1991). The origins of black hostility to the police. *Policing and Society*, 2(1), 1-15. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10439463.1991.9964628>
- Stack, S. J., & Cao, L. (1998). Political conservatism and confidence in the police: A comparative analysis. *Journal of Crime and Justice*, 21(1), 71-76.
- Surette, R. (2010). *Media, crime, and criminal justice: Images, realities and policies* (3rd ed.). Thompson/Wadsworth Publishing
- Thomas, C.W. & Hyman, J.M. (1977). Perceptions of crime, fear of victimization, and public perceptions of police performance. *Journal of Police Science and Administration*, 5(3), 305-317.
- Tyler, T. R. (2004). Enhancing police legitimacy. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 593(), 84-99. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4127668>.
- Verma, A. (1999). Cultural roots of police corruption in India. *Policing. An International Journal of Police Strategies & Management*, 22(3), 264-279. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13639519910285044>

- Walker, D., Richardson, R.J., Denyer, T., & Williams, O. (1972). Contact and support: An empirical assessment of public attitudes toward the police and the courts. *North Carolina Law Review*, 51(1), 43-79. <https://scholarship.law.unc.edu/nclr/vol51/iss1/7>.
- Walker, S. (1997). Complaints against the police: A focus group study of citizen perceptions, goals, and expectations. *Criminal Justice Review*, 22(2), 207-226. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F073401689702200205>
- Webb, V.J., & Marshall, C.E. (1995). The relative importance of race and ethnicity on citizen attitudes toward the police. *American Journal of Police*, 14(2), 45-66. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07358549510102749>
- Weinrath, M., Young, J., & Kohm, S. (2012). Attitudes toward the criminal justice system in a high crime Canadian community. *Canadian Journal of Urban Research*, 21(2), 112-131. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26193915>
- Worrall, J.L. (1999). Public perceptions of police efficacy and image: The 'fuzziness' of support for the police. *American Journal of Criminal Justice*, 24(1), 47-66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02887617>
- Wu, Y., Sun, I.Y., & Triplett, R.A. (2009). Race, class or neighbourhood context: Which matters more in measuring satisfaction with police? *Justice Quarterly*, 26(1), 125-156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07418820802119950>
- Zothansanga, D. (2012). *Police administration in Mizoram 1987-2005*. [Doctoral dissertation, Mizoram University]. Research Direct.